

INTERNATIONAL SALES DATA ANALYSIS USING CLOUDERA, ORACLE VIRTUAL MACHINE: USING BIG DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS FOR INTERNATIONAL SALES PROSPECTS

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Introduction. The sales business is one of the main spheres that analytics are interested in. Because the insights derived from sales data can bring huge profit to businesses and improve the business operations to get maximum value from trades.

Nowadays, not local trade but international trade is interesting business people more and more. Due to globalization, the doors to the market of the whole world are open for businessman. The improvement of transportation, communication, and online transactions technologies has improved the international trade conditions. Now entrepreneurs from one corner of the world can do the trade in another corner without any obstacles.

Thus, sales, market, trade etc. data analysis now is being done not only for local markets but for international market as well. Aggregate data about the trade processes of whole world is available on different data sources. They just need to be analysed and useful insights are needed to be extracted. The results can further be implemented for decision making process of businesses that are planning to go international.

But need to be mentioned that the world sales, trade, and transactions datasets are not small in size. The size of data is very big and very complicated. They cannot be analysed using simple analytics tools like Excel, power BI and so on. They must be analysed using special big data analytics and visualization software.

Therefore, in this project it has been decided to do big data analysis in terms of world sales and transactions data. And we are willing to extract meaningful information and give some suggestions to business people who are planning to do sales and trade worldwide.

Data definition

The dataset has been downloaded from E for Excel website through following URL: <https://eforexcel.com/wp/downloads-18-sample-csv-files-data-sets-for-testing-sales/> The web page contains a range of datasets about the sales with different sizes. For this project the biggest dataset with the size of 196.98 MB has been downloaded. Although the size of downloaded zip file is just 196.98 MB, the actual dataset's size after unzipping is 595 MB. The dataset contains information about the sales records of almost all countries all around the world, with 14 attributes included. The total number of records is 5 million. This is sample, transactional data, dedicated to be used for analysis and testing on analytical software

The attributes

The dataset contains 14 attributes (columns):

- 1) Country: The data column that indicates in which country the sales has been done. The record of sales in 185 countries has been done in this dataset.
- 2) Item type: The grouped types of items sold and bought have been recorded under this column. In total there are 12 item types: Baby food, Beverages, Cereal, Clothes, Cosmetics, Fruits, Household, meat, Office Supplies, Personal Care, Snacks and Vegetables.
- 3) Order date: the dates of orders starting from November 7th 2013 to September 2nd 2020, the dataset covers the sales for almost 7 years.
- 4) Order ID: unique ID numbers for each order, with 9 digits value.

5) Order priority: The orders are prioritized in 4 categories: H C L M – critical, high, medium and low

6) Region: Each country stated in the first column belongs to one particular region: Asia, Australia and Oceania, Central America and Caribbean, Europe, Middle East and North Africa, Sub-Saharan Africa. Total 7 regions

7) Sales channels: the channel through which the sales have been done: Online or Offline.

8) Ship date: the dates of Shipment of orders in between December 27th 2013 and October 30th 2020.

9) Total revenue: total revenue from sales

10) Total cost: total cost of sales

11) Total profit: revenue-costs=profit earned from the sales.

12) Unit cost: how much does each ordered product costs

13) Unit price: the price of each sold item

14) Units sold: the number of units sold in each order Below in the table, the tabular representation of statistics for all numeric attributes are given.

Dashboard implementation

For data visualisation, a special tool: AWS QuickSight tool has been used. After creating the account on AWS, the registration to QuickSight has also been done. Afterwards the data from the local downloads folder has been added to QuickSight. Further the data visualisation has been done, which will be discussed in the next part of the report.

Results

Following are some of the results obtained and visualised using above mentioned data tools:

Based on the pie chart above, it can be seen that the biggest proportion of international trade is going in Europe, Sub-Saharan Africa and Asia. And the least product trades have occurred in North America and Australia & Oceania. Thus, the answer is ready: enterprises will benefit by doing trade either in Europe, or in Sub-Saharan Africa or in Asia, three big continents of the earth.

The order records based on order date shows that the sales had quite fluctuating but stable linear trend within 7 years. The fluctuation can be due to aggregation of worldwide sales data and thus seasonality might not be extracted. However, some useful insights can be found. For example, highest day with biggest proportion of sales records is Jun 3, 2016 with average Units Sold of 511,908.45%, while the lowest day is Dec 3, 2015 with average Units Sold of 487,580.64%

Year-to-date total count of records for Sep 10, 2020 increased by 0.34% (1,102) from \$323,772 to \$324,874

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